

FOS like 1, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (FOSL1) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

FOSL1 is one of the four members of the FOS gene family. These genes encode leucine zipper proteins that can dimerize with proteins of the JUN family, thereby forming the transcription factor complex AP-1. FOS proteins act as regulators of cell proliferation, differentiation, and transformation. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 FOSL1 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for FOSL1-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr FOSL1 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of 71C_3 (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search down by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order FOSL1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. FOS like 1, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (FOSL1)

FOSL1 (alias Fos-related antigen 1 or FRA-1), is one of the four members of the FOS gene family. Matsui et al. [4] isolated cDNA clones of human FRA-1/2 by screening human c-DNA libraries with human fos DNA as a probe. They obtained human FRA-1 cDNA clones that could code for a protein of 271 amino acid residues with a calculated molecular weight of 29,413 and showed 90% similarity with rat FRA-1 protein. FOSL1 (FRA-1) encodes leucine zipper proteins that can dimerize with proteins of the JUN family, thus forming the transcription factor complex AP-1.

The basic leucine zipper domain (bZIP domain) is found in many DNA binding eukaryotic proteins, one part of which mediates sequence specific DNA binding properties and the leucine zipper that is required to hold together (dimerize) two DNA binding regions (Ellenberger [5] and Vinson et al. [6]). The human metallothionein IIa (hMTII_A) gene responds to induction by heavy metals and by steroid hormones through the action of metal regulatory elements (MRE) and glucocorticoid responsive elements (GRE). Lee et al. [7] report the identification of two cellular DNA-binding proteins that interact selectively with sequences governing the basal level expression of hMTII_A, one of which is a novel activator protein (AP-1) that interacts with sequences in the basal level enhancer (BLE) of hMTII_A and also binds to a site within the 72-base pair (bp) repeats of the simian virus 40 (SV40) enhancer region. The structure of AP-1 is a heterodimer composed of proteins belonging to the c-Fos, c-Jun, ATF and JDP families and the AP-1 family consists of several bZIP domain proteins, the Jun, the Fos, and the ATF subfamilies, which all have to dimerize before they can bind to their DNA target sites (Wagner [8]). The nuclear transcription factor AP-1, controls cellular events including cell transformation, proliferation, differentiation and apoptosis (Ameyar et al. [9]). Pognonec et al. [10] found that FRA-1 interacted with USF (a basic-helix-loop-helix-leucine zipper (bHLHZip) protein). Expression of exogenous USF led to a decrease in AP-1 dependent transcription in F9 cells and co-expression of exogenous FRA-1 restored the AP-1 activity in a dose-dependent manner.

FRA-1 seems to play a role in the progression of many carcinomas and FRA-1 over-expression enhances the motility and invasion of breast and colorectal cancer cells, but inhibits the tumorigenicity of cervical carcinoma cell lines (Milde-Langosch [11]). In this research work, I present 3rd order combinations of FOSL1 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [12]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [12].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one

recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7_1C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a

strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 FOSL1-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [13]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [14] and martinez implementation in Martinez [15] and Baudin et al. [16]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested FOSL1-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving FOSL1 were obtained from a full set of ${}^71C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of JUN-FOSL1-X combinations

Eferl and Wagner [17] review that AP-1 is a dimeric transcription factor that contains members from the JUN, FOS, ATF and MAF protein families. Further, two components of AP-1 i.e, c-JUN and c-FOS, were first identified as viral oncoproteins, so their role in tumorigenesis is well established. Placentation establishes the maternal-fetal interface and is required for successful pregnancy. The epithelial component of

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-FRZB	17	35368	17731	25382	51767	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	24	25444	38488	23401	24549
CSNK1D-FGF4-FOSL1	30	6054	51426	42593	32863	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	88	36639	18548	29008	12844
CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1	171	44847	19116	31051	26950	CTBP2-CTNNB1-FOSL1	193	49920	22884	20817	52920
CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	255	24314	35136	31526	39110	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	256	39545	1842	16944	18375
FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP4	292	44876	11834	15903	36394	DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	326	21740	41468	36036	47108
FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	349	31659	11861	10245	21849	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	359	18070	3202	3757	21594
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	372	34237	49971	11736	48629	FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	378	3397	2566	2260	40025
FOSL1-FOXNI-FRZB	426	18495	3914	3925	50337	DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1	432	8047	21605	31028	45972
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT4	455	37570	20729	10105	38487	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	458	25557	50663	10786	1378
FBXW11-FGF4-FOSL1	485	34731	55734	37270	13666	APC-BCL9-FOSL1	503	44276	12767	10482	56943
CSNK1D-FOSL1-FZD1	568	999	47773	10250	51091	DVL2-FGF4-FOSL1	664	42437	30359	29718	55333
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT2B	670	19667	46545	40946	19709	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	675	26389	36474	6816	48298
FOSL1-FOXNI-SFRP4	680	23049	4982	9425	19314	FOSL1-WIF1-WNT2B	727	2770	23114	37617	17980
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	731	20058	29538	14504	27891	FOSL1-FOXNI-KREMEN1	742	14009	6113	8523	21187
DAAM1-FGF4-FOSL1	749	45182	54951	56379	34801	DKK1-DVL2-FOSL1	754	5173	30314	36187	56024
FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B	802	20624	39428	24273	52148	FOSL1-FOXNI-SEN2	808	25273	3965	4409	8541
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	832	28714	21515	30364	38569	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-RHOU	846	41555	5035	55239	46031
FOSL1-NKD1-SFRP4	875	160	5276	11851	11033	FZD5-DVL2-FOSL1	982	7285	6435	17317	49867
FOSL1-FOXNI-GSK3B	983	14647	1776	17080	41173	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	996	16387	31797	50574	23742
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	1000	17132	38816	29827	1621	FOSL1-FZD2-SFRP4	1024	10811	26104	3869	54533
CSNK1G1-DVL2-FOSL1	1061	14048	12622	34641	48959	FOSL1-FOXNI-PPP2CA	1072	22257	16994	9632	25457
CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	1094	46700	26853	25310	54546	FOSL1-FZD7-PPP2CA	1103	37962	25642	24479	50931
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	1246	18255	19691	45038	20105	FOSL1-FOXNI-SLC9A3R1	1275	28011	885	4881	51370
FOSL1-FOXNI-FZD8	1314	19509	2343	16192	19984	FOSL1-GSK3A-SEN2	1322	23410	370	29385	29247
CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FOSL1	1324	32995	31993	33693	996	FOSL1-PORCN-RHOU	1333	44749	10281	23020	23848
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	1368	22243	14796	45725	54959	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2B	1381	1526	2254	11678	47870
FOSL1-FOXNI-LRP5	1396	12463	8896	42948	43152	DVL1-FBXW11-FOSL1	1398	33771	7304	14350	55345
APC-FGF4-FOSL1	1403	38742	14424	52151	37505	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	1425	3331	440	49507	31594
FOSL1-GSK3A-SFRP4	1436	32274	8539	22527	42270	FOSL1-PORCN-TLE2	1446	44769	21226	13796	30066
CTBP1-FGF4-FOSL1	1455	29082	37073	39831	41035	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	1479	1306	37107	54515	12375
FOSL1-FOXNI-TLE2	1506	19146	2341	7352	15489	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	1512	2335	4160	3374	12963
AES-EP300-FOSL1	1521	46072	48935	20712	49058	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	1542	4890	20754	29478	5342
CSNK2A1-CTBP1-FOSL1	1581	35982	53710	47786	1954	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	1606	10313	45532	19498	50800
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	1656	55025	38932	40354	51107	FOSL1-FOXNI-RHOU	1660	21880	3384	19296	29104
BCL9-FGF4-FOSL1	1679	19298	42532	40993	55112	FOSL1-GSK3A-GSK3B	1690	15629	2644	46105	37164
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	1708	28629	15238	40456	52065	FZD5-FGF4-FOSL1	1718	8030	21299	33264	34465
FZD5-CCND3-FOSL1	1721	5130	11993	34398	15331	FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP1	1757	36317	8057	17969	48972
FOSL1-GSK3A-LRP5	1793	5589	2949	32274	52490	CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	1800	15338	42242	52718	32578
FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4	1801	30399	19599	18597	6617	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	1834	22981	29680	27665	50575
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	1842	39537	26432	55090	52175	FOSL1-NKD1-PPP2CA	1845	14335	40783	24581	23211
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	1846	2471	1853	521	54004	FOSL1-PORCN-FBXW4	1896	35711	18446	8569	19117
FOSL1-PORCN-PPP2CA	1917	33808	39279	26918	22451	CSNK1G1-FGF4-FOSL1	1936	28205	33826	36195	48093
FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SFRP4	1952	52448	1955	16120	30096	FOSL1-FOXNI-WNT5A	2034	6923	6744	9847	23516
FOSL1-FOXNI-TCF7L1	2041	16265	2181	10149	12942	CSNK1D-FOSL1-SEN2	2088	21782	40398	32697	32527
FOSL1-FOXNI-WNT2B	2092	14363	2122	5400	9642	FZD5-CCND2-FOSL1	2169	34455	22205	26665	51389
APC-CCND3-FOSL1	2190	27032	11642	22161	35558	CSNK1A1-FGF4-FOSL1	2196	29619	53247	49107	51945
DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	2248	20750	40597	26220	53540	FOSL1-FOXNI-FZD6	2256	14824	19723	8486	53548
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7L1	2280	27789	13184	15773	14755	DVL1-FGF4-FOSL1	2292	40318	18510	24845	19218
FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	2296	35937	10116	9410	31529	FOSL1-MYC-SFRP4	2339	42470	6026	33033	29120
FOSL1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	2355	22861	911	45587	39936	FOSL1-FZD2-GSK3B	2382	12778	19494	45692	50453
FOSL1-FOXNI-FZD1	2391	9360	6982	9851	31253	FOSL1-FZD7-WNT2B	2454	17850	39272	36856	49039
FOSL1-NKD1-SEN2	2466	6869	5781	10026	30259	FOSL1-FOXNI-TCF7	2473	12271	1932	11488	24676
FOSL1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	2483	39419	13608	18592	31025	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT3A	2512	4481	499	34674	10423
FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A	2570	6332	206	39656	6459	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT4	2598	5807	2371	11336	21308
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7	2655	29633	37738	24610	27978	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2R1A	2696	46872	41797	35276	27908
FOSL1-FOXNI-LRP6	2703	18423	9454	15846	43299	FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7	2828	29087	33743	34368	53991
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-FOSL1	2849	847	23417	33270	57047	FOSL1-FOXNI-WNT4	2926	19268	4984	7030	42733
DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB	2954	10112	50811	45748	42692	FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4	2957	29593	15781	53739	51686
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	3017	11044	1525	53908	3915	FOSL1-FOXNI-MYC	3046	33641	23663	11459	46671
FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2	3080	12766	6760	15272	13494	FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	3142	34552	21454	20799	55831
FOSL1-FOXNI-FBXW4	3153	30885	23159	9810	3473	FGF4-FOSL1-PPP2CA	3175	29507	37541	48577	51007
FOSL1-GSK3A-PITX2	3246	8961	918	7353	12922	FOSL1-FOXNI-WNT2	3267	27111	6567	10866	26206
FGF4-FOSL1-FZD1	3290	40378	18437	35554	52267	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2CA	3303	25232	24882	2685	4764

Table 1: Rankings of FOSL1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

the placenta consists of trophoblast cells, which possess the capacity for multilineage differentiation and are responsible for placenta-specific functions. FOSL1 contributes to the regulation of placental development. Kubota et al. [18] showed through

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-FRZB	18486	33706	51536	16007	42608	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	15910	20828	47008	39310	20122
CSNK1D-FGF4-FOSL1	3694	6645	6799	4138	45840	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	27232	42351	44650	16863	48178
CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1	19400	39101	15057	5353	6829	CTBP2-CTNNB1-FOSL1	22087	47806	43102	26570	12950
CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	52227	34156	6226	46113	43359	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	36531	47500	56688	1297	8711
FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP4	1126	41952	37755	38422	51768	DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	14095	26375	3333	23119	42212
FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	314	29835	38646	3075	34319	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	41514	24088	54636	21014	19349
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	29015	37923	40684	6763	23547	FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	46914	7268	50547	1274	44200
FOSL1-FOXN1-FRZB	1736	15846	50466	9743	17620	DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1	4252	18471	3345	22302	52225
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT4	4252	18471	3345	22302	52225	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	15271	29847	41615	22047	48378
FBXW1-FGF4-FOSL1	9717	17062	12881	5316	18991	APC-BCL9-FOSL1	26374	51523	20691	9548	17725
CSNK1D-FOSL1-FZD1	14359	1015	37515	5753	14234	DVL2-FGF4-FOSL1	3167	48007	8628	17742	42623
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT2B	4296	5489	1279	29512	55035	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	33776	19243	42932	10498	52900
FOSL1-FRAT1-SFRP4	3581	13413	50450	24051	14731	FOSL1-WIF1-WNT2B	41773	13018	2276	54404	49689
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	46607	15174	26086	25252	40912	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	2901	4767	41791	45598	13163
DAAMI-FGF4-FOSL1	2515	51205	7449	23613	7495	DKK1-DVL2-FOSL1	32822	15198	12108	3507	28223
FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B	21116	7705	2123	56839	56883	FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2	1644	24800	52856	5786	32696
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	36692	36234	15133	298	43524	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-RHOU	19254	49825	54278	50968	41085
FOSL1-NKD1-SFRP4	38557	1693	50390	24818	21820	FZD5-DVL2-FOSL1	31108	15865	56297	1825	46027
FOSL1-FOXN1-GSK3B	31108	15865	56297	1825	46027	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	31108	15865	56297	1825	46027
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	5134	9823	24616	52464	27691	FOSL1-FZD2-SFRP4	4647	1210	36429	2252	17735
CSNK1G1-DVL2-FOSL1	24608	32567	25022	2699	31491	FOSL1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	2050	20570	56654	7068	31115
CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	18872	46435	17556	11771	54033	FOSL1-FZD7-PPP2CA	54451	46826	3194	28518	28447
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	6305	18815	46524	19747	38837	FOSL1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	3153	36795	52930	36241	48302
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD8	2757	28761	55000	20964	54956	FOSL1-GSK3A-SEN2	3309	21823	56135	50608	24479
CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FOSL1	26592	26504	31836	43474	14209	FOSL1-PORCN-RHOU	1550	39845	36998	42942	56120
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	553	41867	29836	8057	53097	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2B	8040	5830	31727	31	46871
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP5	6494	8694	40579	24357	5973	DVL1-FBXW1-FOSL1	19045	18319	56904	35	28285
APC-FGF4-FOSL1	11913	34261	19328	3356	53756	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	20492	705	35136	30860	53018
FOSL1-GSK3A-SFRP4	6589	36249	56048	37361	34223	FOSL1-PORCN-TLE2	11375	42064	44489	3406	53873
CTBP1-FGF4-FOSL1	4851	14275	24640	778	55018	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	42099	14135	52254	57017	24935
FOSL1-NKD1-TLE2	2685	18230	45559	25782	35344	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	51755	5242	44005	49978	52983
AES-EP300-FOSL1	43507	49548	17732	5048	38399	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	37744	27522	48171	53533	24924
CSNK2A1-CTBP1-FOSL1	48595	20470	4367	24006	8607	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	50831	2200	13168	50933	31960
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	4014	52588	15864	2361	53651	FOSL1-FOXN1-RHOU	1989	10797	48585	37026	31459
BCL9-FGF4-FOSL1	17209	16838	16284	7375	47320	FOSL1-GSK3A-GSK3B	1419	30732	55587	54721	53577
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	39137	42805	45435	35330	23074	FZD5-FGF4-FOSL1	3050	25364	36566	13304	54934
FZD5-CCND3-FOSL1	38034	34654	56227	16297	18221	FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP1	10522	38362	29766	6077	55724
FOSL1-GSK3A-LRP5	14584	286	49671	55368	36879	CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	53822	4385	5771	55698	30961
FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4	28709	31696	9585	5972	36656	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	2494	21424	29421	5565	13873
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	36045	19108	7369	17738	6729	FOSL1-NKD1-PPP2CA	21934	29546	42661	35675	17456
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	34233	941	55096	25592	35663	FOSL1-PORCN-FBXW4	996	45964	6696	11811	50330
FOSL1-PORCN-PPP2CA	857	51996	6161	7188	48966	CSNK1G1-FGF4-FOSL1	30497	29781	8021	11753	43558
FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SFRP4	50064	57024	56666	31648	53883	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT5A	5307	14590	45152	44826	55367
FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7L1	502	20490	56294	30140	13635	CSNK1D-FOSL1-SEN2	20750	28948	9391	39658	39465
FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2B	3731	11944	46580	2296	53387	FZD5-CCND2-FOSL1	3513	41975	54460	12813	30675
APC-CCND3-FOSL1	43650	23498	55526	7318	50103	CSNK1A1-FGF4-FOSL1	16622	30625	6828	2304	55529
DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	33541	20184	16489	26495	35744	FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD6	4046	6143	29686	14520	37535
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7L1	731	8052	33790	38315	51524	DVL1-FGF4-FOSL1	17015	27364	12609	5371	33295
FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	4646	17601	54904	1115	45855	FOSL1-MYC-SFRP4	2575	51076	50017	35470	8587
FOSL1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	12185	33599	52257	41997	37270	FOSL1-FZD2-GSK3B	5098	22623	40747	48566	47602
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD1	1950	8922	42094	2898	13807	FOSL1-FZD7-WNT2B	50187	4425	4093	55495	52155
FOSL1-NKD1-SEN2	15372	3697	55084	25337	9352	FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7	1675	7202	46849	34237	39333
FOSL1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	7522	46541	51243	1546	46102	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT3A	9692	5532	35479	30879	13078
FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A	40808	8862	52958	56668	7351	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT4	4799	4228	46889	440	32783
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7	851	19236	7477	4033	41750	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2R1A	20816	55928	16147	47523	47242
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP6	8216	12122	52031	24335	23358	FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7	6118	26200	9358	53523	34103
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-FOSL1	34000	288	23729	11736	43862	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT4	2275	8743	50316	14275	47768
DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB	15443	4827	12607	32034	48635	FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4	34496	9590	20805	42045	6769
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	5655	3612	51883	54394	46466	FOSL1-FOXN1-MYC	7089	25106	47390	44956	48333
FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2	7001	10490	53012	815	33966	FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	7001	10490	53012	815	33966
FOSL1-FOXN1-FBXW4	3141	36195	30061	7895	5125	FGF4-FOSL1-PPP2CA	42277	28170	8091	25442	19223
FOSL1-GSK3A-PITX2	22118	26574	53921	57069	41599	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2	4844	21073	49643	390	10186
FGF4-FOSL1-FZD1	39663	26051	18681	32329	5201	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2CA	21063	49029	6511	48244	44672

Table 2: Rankings of FOSL1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

co-immunoprecipitation, co-immunolocalization, and ChIP analyses, that FOSL1 interacted with JUNB and, to a lesser extent, JUN in differentiating trophoblast cells. Knockdown of FOSL1 and JUNB expression inhibited both endocrine and invasive properties of trophoblast cells. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-FRZB	48750	46940	49058	47805	7521	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2P2	11214	7586	5074	7384	41915
CSNK1D-FGF4-FOSL1	31433	17351	34702	49796	3779	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2P2	9857	21302	3091	25681	49127
CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1	47946	1732	38933	38678	23755	CTBP2-CTNNB1-FOSL1	12477	34215	13015	7117	42120
CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	33024	20784	45045	33319	8066	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2P2	17310	2495	82	9104	48865
FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP4	44543	52571	34231	46029	13871	DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2P2	3431	3346	23554	20246	9046
FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2P2	54760	25670	47342	32899	26575	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2P2	13461	35727	546	20026	44857
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	11661	37114	3277	931	53168	FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	11701	13725	13502	3308	41595
FOSL1-FOXN1-FRZB	4845	4217	9346	8710	50240	DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1	56316	11460	37809	55590	6360
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT4	47380	31804	36756	47696	19151	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2P2	51877	55400	52885	34018	3734
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	32715	28640	35906	29158	11589	APC-BCL9-FOSL1	15337	18912	25043	17653	30357
CSNK1D-FOSL1-FZD1	33939	40307	29863	45255	32407	DVL2-FGF4-FOSL1	28814	41386	42144	48902	4193
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT2B	9686	2290	2189	14059	39340	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	50038	6818	42415	47626	4928
FOSL1-FOXN1-SFRP4	45107	48753	50599	52560	3992	FOSL1-WIF1-WNT2B	25173	2114	24567	1335	44580
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	13778	2749	16108	6403	43145	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	5566	2122	4725	4323	49299
DAAMI-FGF4-FOSL1	39718	54241	55152	47140	6015	DKK1-DVL2-FOSL1	53868	6384	55605	30940	12601
FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B	36889	18888	44664	53547	13962	FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2P2	50427	48059	30743	46224	6709
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	37417	42346	33119	29950	927	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-RHOU	40904	5712	55181	51304	16176
FOSL1-NKD1-SFRP4	26523	39016	6871	18225	44405	FZD5-DVL2-FOSL1	40182	25866	35056	29369	7043
FOSL1-FOXN1-GSK3B	284	8167	4904	8619	50083	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	49067	35754	42264	40921	9123
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	4213	41297	24152	15364	47738	FOSL1-FZD2-SFRP4	25818	32267	25224	27273	48695
CSNK1G1-DVL2-FOSL1	13304	16111	11364	20166	55668	FOSL1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	51329	15073	48971	51617	23899
CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	25168	1437	11571	16056	25721	FOSL1-FZD7-PPP2CA	35591	32520	50960	44000	21144
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	50590	19180	53417	52474	6976	FOSL1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	34742	13119	54271	41553	7238
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD8	18145	45592	11421	12903	51267	FOSL1-GSK3A-SEN2P2	11356	7709	5408	9588	41158
CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FOSL1	7348	26679	6679	8520	40678	FOSL1-PORCN-RHOU	2397	31652	9884	24315	30810
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	52810	50470	34544	37927	3516	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2B	27112	14023	16313	6628	52241
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP5	19194	9612	13710	10552	49252	DVL1-FBXW11-FOSL1	1086	49040	10558	27196	54543
APC-FGF4-FOSL1	39629	40499	37919	40405	7494	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	42013	9877	52887	52662	11462
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	24080	48870	2981	6458	47742	FOSL1-PORCN-TLE2	11344	44887	618	8380	48021
CTBP1-FGF4-FOSL1	30113	26329	54976	56153	8704	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	29544	47341	44123	52018	7644
FOSL1-FOXN1-TLE2	10111	34166	2997	1459	46410	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	43309	33771	50006	38500	4467
AES-EP300-FOSL1	27689	20431	21551	25851	56678	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	10579	5753	10670	19639	21636
CSNK2A1-CTBP1-FOSL1	51466	6276	44543	34556	2632	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	31351	10581	42739	34529	664
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	28028	36636	4319	2494	42274	FOSL1-FOXN1-RHOU	6665	9152	26476	10977	50432
BCL9-FGF4-FOSL1	101	1534	21498	16607	27262	FOSL1-GSK3A-GSK3B	53394	55855	50166	49917	857
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	43183	49105	41385	39275	5077	FZD5-FGF4-FOSL1	46553	12322	55789	43921	10970
FZD5-CCND3-FOSL1	4245	7266	11704	15340	18858	FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP1	12651	4591	23008	11171	43358
FOSL1-GSK3A-LRP5	41882	45860	41982	56323	1496	CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	45823	54747	52368	41434	48001
FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4	13997	8027	15717	17898	52096	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	3396	43706	23582	7101	52388
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	10083	6588	8685	24287	30035	FOSL1-NKD1-PPP2CA	2142	38096	5085	20731	35691
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	43758	21393	56612	37171	12178	FOSL1-PORCN-FBXW4	19295	6262	4610	7514	13534
FOSL1-PORCN-PPP2CA	48261	18485	32801	52162	23392	CSNK1G1-FGF4-FOSL1	8963	28835	12476	27024	48361
FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SFRP4	11157	1063	12252	1915	27364	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT5A	8341	10381	8155	9375	49603
FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7L1	6256	50988	4857	10230	51120	CSNK1D-FOSL1-SEN2P2	27384	17302	26341	7301	43654
FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2B	1186	35009	15480	12827	50006	FZD5-CCND2-FOSL1	13152	46996	20245	4220	49402
APC-CCND3-FOSL1	14004	19135	18446	27673	7344	CSNK1A1-FGF4-FOSL1	31936	30526	31908	35528	15251
DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	3553	54257	16310	25765	12367	FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD6	13640	15481	10464	19959	46450
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7L1	14669	55	993	18720	27063	DVL1-FGF4-FOSL1	45386	4232	46196	56492	27411
FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	47297	50999	30260	50806	4015	FOSL1-MYC-SFRP4	48771	44097	44821	42504	15359
FOSL1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	1409	42580	3372	20682	38693	FOSL1-FZD2-GSK3B	30096	21061	34538	29703	9399
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD1	25925	10874	2904	9032	52484	FOSL1-FZD7-WNT2B	21619	45	3513	13198	43493
FOSL1-NKD1-SEN2P2	16870	1004	11411	25457	43247	FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7	49708	52975	52794	35953	2727
FOSL1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	37873	50909	52614	49669	43825	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT3A	15630	39992	11099	5546	48850
FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A	14577	48454	4103	4489	48405	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT4	41560	17077	46101	51615	8307
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7	30681	31215	55178	44882	16830	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2R1A	21985	646	17395	14514	28922
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP6	37870	47647	43468	46668	7859	FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7	2040	20827	11649	18240	45367
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-FOSL1	43122	17498	29136	41748	25756	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT4	53448	12	54578	41681	9465
DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB	53609	2816	40791	31392	44680	FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4	20560	6324	9945	23630	45285
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	52307	56531	47402	55645	3684	FOSL1-FOXN1-MYC	10915	26427	7515	6321	53618
FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2	34611	47563	33805	56132	5656	FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	4534	8444	3333	12890	53657
FOSL1-FOXN1-FBXW4	22313	44309	2923	15637	49928	FGF4-FOSL1-PPP2CA	2668	4065	11722	25274	53689
FOSL1-GSK3A-PITX2	3336	36071	6692	8964	29002	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2	47191	48365	52960	44342	6468
FGF4-FOSL1-FZD1	32182	13714	52916	30292	9916	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2CA	47425	55951	39423	37994	17117

Table 3: Rankings of FOSL1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

combinations for JUN along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1, FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1, FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4, FOSL1-JUN-SEN2P2, FOSL1-JUN-TCF7, FOSL1-JUN-PITX2, FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A, FOSL1-JUN-PPP2R1A and FOSL1-JUN-PPP2CA. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FOSL1-FRAT1-FRZB	14761	1621	35448	7423	9102	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2P	39777	6057	7944	11007	26753
CSNK1D-FGF4-FOSL1	39220	16866	389	23848	23132	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2P	7660	26757	51210	21967	12513
CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1	7660	26757	51210	21967	12513	CTBP2-CTNNB1-FOSL1	50282	51309	48755	8945	52707
CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	12098	31961	43639	23246	42209	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2P	53756	53724	17611	16937	2010
FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP4	7834	33798	49219	25475	52140	DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2P	39859	13212	23188	18065	7821
FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2P	12075	2582	50306	27092	37213	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2P	39240	18008	8851	50840	47605
FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4	40993	13521	5723	19915	17592	FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	45098	10285	6164	24489	8061
FOSL1-FOXN1-FRZB	36987	50279	6665	29743	28829	DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1	32358	1547	51613	20266	23707
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT4	7917	37593	48481	35640	51574	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2P	11684	1590	49191	41693	56255
FBXW11-FGF4-FOSL1	41676	33901	5574	20414	20305	APC-BCL9-FOSL1	19605	5233	17989	52855	5421
CSNK1D-FOSL1-FZD1	41680	37855	2054	46155	46394	DVL2-FGF4-FOSL1	16675	24385	35779	29931	14623
FOSL1-PORCN-WNT2B	51756	54848	26032	20042	1751	FOSL1-FRAT1-TLE2	15082	2010	33027	18895	57055
FOSL1-FOXN1-SFRP4	11238	13543	43498	33908	10953	FOSL1-WIF1-WNT2B	12903	16845	50910	16896	7421
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	9338	19582	40214	46514	45765	FOSL1-FOXN1-KREMEN1	6535	4193	12656	15365	2682
DAAMI1-FGF4-FOSL1	52419	47570	24971	2355	30167	DKK1-DVL2-FOSL1	15814	18959	41955	55956	38254
FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B	6277	10803	37453	46689	25622	FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2P	16250	40283	38179	32075	20042
FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4	8229	28251	25524	20028	51893	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-RHOU	7680	16304	49608	19854	56619
FOSL1-NKD1-SFRP4	46318	21183	12035	36344	30342	FZD5-DVL2-FOSL1	12766	39845	28395	31267	55884
FOSL1-FOXN1-GSK3B	17098	3338	10035	12874	4259	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	9174	53008	50222	47253	30596
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	7033	46161	34317	46961	357	FOSL1-FZD2-SFRP4	38137	54230	51403	21959	6260
CSNK1G1-DVL2-FOSL1	8083	52720	54665	44734	52383	FOSL1-FOXN1-PPP2CA	21982	3651	43234	19001	11166
CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	3540	41011	53892	1277	30939	FOSL1-FZD7-PPP2CA	7623	24057	41611	37347	7700
FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1	15407	495	42575	35576	56798	FOSL1-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	6293	20325	34022	31771	12589
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD8	11298	1385	13720	14297	6541	FOSL1-GSK3A-SEN2P	52420	10321	6858	40709	10270
CSNK2A1-CTNNB1-FOSL1	14159	29263	5533	12508	51686	FOSL1-PORCN-RHOU	21806	54658	25822	20528	2159
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	56003	23413	39066	3360	54945	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2B	16777	24758	43097	23275	38302
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP5	45040	47246	14065	24765	5919	DVL1-FBXW11-FOSL1	1709	4318	7678	54275	43756
APC-FGF4-FOSL1	53198	33392	49548	38176	39685	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	14329	18478	43731	32209	46898
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	47417	18884	16591	12561	21187	FOSL1-PORCN-TLE2	54214	44956	26881	18144	5869
CTBP1-FGF4-FOSL1	18973	13392	19431	40916	29565	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	6068	2098	52232	48612	54047
FOSL1-GSK3A-TLE2	48872	8854	6882	23880	54238	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	14627	8003	43826	49427	54343
AES-EP300-FOSL1	2076	9358	40678	41334	55550	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	50101	9229	37322	47023	17545
CSNK2A1-CTBP1-FOSL1	55694	34498	49182	54478	10195	FOSL1-FRAT1-LRP5	6391	34980	35339	17352	9847
EP300-FGF4-FOSL1	33196	23070	26711	8374	5298	FOSL1-FOXN1-RHOU	52304	13418	6434	16650	5417
BCL9-FGF4-FOSL1	23710	41624	29756	12744	1383	FOSL1-GSK3A-GSK3B	9054	924	43468	34377	40355
FOSL1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	7788	54446	47795	43434	54055	FZD5-FGF4-FOSL1	14470	54659	17002	25143	6754
FZD5-CCND3-FOSL1	45912	55459	47401	53552	2164	FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP1	54293	34318	31561	16647	17560
FOSL1-GSK3A-LRP5	7373	56066	39032	34673	45412	CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	44523	32024	5826	41353	32438
FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4	19744	56004	29879	48791	49954	DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1	54614	11564	51051	37580	52640
FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1	53680	15862	18440	42387	14908	FOSL1-NKD1-PPP2CA	45879	24082	5855	50930	2635
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	20605	4506	43594	44065	56286	FOSL1-PORCN-FBXW4	51245	47518	29410	28956	4946
FOSL1-PORCN-PPP2CA	8604	37919	49115	19867	23808	CSNK1G1-FGF4-FOSL1	3966	11339	26512	6277	5337
FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SFRP4	40500	53353	26998	9354	15844	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT5A	52174	12235	9794	10821	15555
FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7L1	51148	14470	6099	18679	44903	CSNK1D-FOSL1-SEN2P	23107	16562	29759	43345	40650
FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2B	6875	20315	11938	17724	5955	FZD5-CCND2-FOSL1	9876	40029	41565	5412	1435
APC-CCND3-FOSL1	34348	3788	35248	19616	18892	CSNK1A1-FGF4-FOSL1	42045	529	1485	3037	46681
DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1	35900	23175	16488	8823	46105	FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD6	44654	4493	8018	16448	39828
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7L1	54580	56035	31769	2449	568	DVL1-FGF4-FOSL1	6347	15617	7599	45586	57107
FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	9587	46756	39612	28530	26972	FOSL1-MYC-SFRP4	19423	11209	44297	2335	42412
FOSL1-GSK3A-PPP2CA	3591	33875	8900	36670	1652	FOSL1-FZD2-GSK3B	8034	30920	53272	45700	8434
FOSL1-FOXN1-FZD1	32171	29385	5507	17423	31092	FOSL1-FZD7-WNT2B	15218	54699	12593	11301	41515
FOSL1-NKD1-SEN2P	48219	21087	6264	51148	5914	FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7	18107	7674	37179	23756	8988
FOSL1-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	7354	10706	50152	28397	23075	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT3A	14387	17574	45609	36527	7338
FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A	49578	2041	33911	51137	47259	FOSL1-WNT1-WNT4	40112	4912	51361	40583	39621
FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7	6864	7571	46905	24216	38937	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2R1A	3192	33424	53266	44332	7085
FOSL1-FOXN1-LRP6	9658	56026	37634	35272	14855	FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7	28853	19246	15764	55796	32910
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-FOSL1	51511	11283	3515	18073	56450	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT4	20287	2448	37360	25562	16564
DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB	15741	22164	14068	24321	14638	FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4	41517	57011	10183	32383	26842
FOSL1-GSK3A-KREMEN1	7377	1898	35969	19960	56231	FOSL1-FOXN1-MYC	26873	54468	16691	8245	45719
FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2	39376	28968	50298	30291	25571	FOSL1-FRAT1-FZD7	48659	16465	5851	11736	27945
FOSL1-FOXN1-FBXW4	46479	18801	18841	8360	35190	FGF4-FOSL1-PPP2CA	34076	11002	7176	22758	44026
FOSL1-GSK3A-PITX2	41751	14274	10983	10196	4550	FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2	19636	209	43294	38004	13421
FGF4-FOSL1-FZD1	7401	19604	37709	30475	42795	FOSL1-JUN-PPP2CA	9738	4179	49861	43749	38763

Table 4: Rankings of FOSL1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of FBX-FOSL1-X combinations

In colorectal carcinoma (CC), Liu et al. [19] established that the expression of FOSL1 was elevated in CC tissues versus adjacent tissues. Functional assays displayed that FOSL1 increased the viability, epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT), migration and invasion of CC cells. Their further investigation demonstrated that FOSL1 was involved in malignant aggressiveness of CC cells by binding to SMAD ubiquitination regulatory factor 1 (SMURF1). Mechanistically, SMURF1 induced F-Box and leucine rich repeat protein 2 (FBXL2) ubiquitination resulted in its degradation, while FBXL2 disrupted the activation of the WNT/ β -catenin signaling. FBXL belongs to F-box and leucine rich repeat proteins. Similarly, FBXW belongs to F-box and WD repeat domain containing proteins. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FBXW family along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FBXW11-FGF4-FOSL1, FOSL1-FRAT1-FBXW4, FOSL1-JUN-FBXW4, FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A, FOSL1-FOXN1-FBXW4, DVL1-FBXW11-FOSL1, and FOSL1-PORCN-FBXW4. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of WNT-FOSL1-X combinations

Yu et al. [20] used transcriptional microarray analysis to examine the expression of WNT signaling components in the spinal cords of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) transgenic SOD1^{G93A} mice at different stages. They found that canonical WNT signaling molecules including WNT-1/3A/7B/8A were up-regulated at 95 days; WNT-10A/16/2/3/7A/7B/9A were all up-regulated at 122 days; WNT-16/8B were down-regulated at middle stage and, noncanonical WNT signaling molecules like WNT4 were up-regulated at 108 days, and WNT-5A/5B/11 were up-regulated at 122 days. At the end stage of the disease, WNT target genes like CCND-1/2/3, EP300, FOSL1, NIK, and PITX2 were all upregulated. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of WNT family along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-FRAT1-WNT4, FOSL1-PORCN-WNT4, FOSL1-PORCN-WNT2B, FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B, FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2B, FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2, FOSL1-FBXW4-WNT3A, FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2, FOSL1-NLK-WNT4, FOSL1-WIF1-WNT2B, FOSL1-WNT1-WNT2B, FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B, FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A, FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A, CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A, FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT5A, FOSL1-FZD7-WNT2B, FOSL1-WNT1-WNT3A, FOSL1-WNT1-WNT4, FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT4, and FOSL1-FOXN1-WNT2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of TCF-FOSL1-X combinations

In perihilar cholangiocarcinoma (PHCC) a type of bile duct cancer, Liu et al. [21] found upregulated expression of TCF7 and with in vitro and in vivo experiments, they showed that c-MYC was a main effector of TCF7 in PHCC cells and responsible for TCF7-induced proliferation, invasion, and migration of PHCC cells. Using qRT-PCR screening, they identified FOSL1 as a downstream target gene of TCF7

and was required in TCF7-induced PHCC proliferation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of TCF family along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1, FOSL1-FRAT1-TCF7L1, FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7L1, FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7L1, FOSL1-PORCN-TCF7, FOSL1-JUN-TCF7, FOSL1-FOXN1-TCF7, and FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FGF-FOSL1-X combinations

Activation of MAP kinase/ERK signalling downstream of fibroblast growth factor (FGF) tyrosine kinase receptors regulates gene expression required for mesoderm induction and patterning of the anteroposterior axis during *Xenopus* development. Cowell et al. [22] investigate the hypothesis that Capicua (Cic) is involved in regulating FGF target gene expression in *Xenopus*. They showed that FGF overexpression or ectodermal wounding, both of which activate ERK, reduced Cic protein levels in embryonic cells. Their transcriptomic analysis identified putative targets of the proposed FGF/ERK/Cic axis: FOS and RAS like family 11 member B (RASL11B), where Cic consensus binding sites are a highly conserved region of intron 1 in the FOS gene and Cic sites in the upstream regions of RASL11B. Both genes are up-regulated by Cic knockdown and FGF4 over-expression. They show that expression of FOS and RASL11B is blocked in the early mesoderm when FGF and ERK signalling is inhibited. The AP-1 components JUN, FOSL1 and ATF3 are also up-regulated by Cic knockdown. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FGF family along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CSNK1D-FGF4-FOSL1, CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1, FBXW11-FGF4-FOSL1, DAAM1-FGF4-FOSL1/CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1, APC-FGF4-FOSL1, CTBP1-FGF4-FOSL1, EP300-FGF4-FOSL1, BCL9-FGF4-FOSL1, FGF4-FOSL1-FRAT1, FGF4-FOSL1-FZD1, DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1, DVL2-FGF4-FOSL1, FZD5-FGF4-FOSL1, DIXDC1-FGF4-FOSL1, CSNK1G1-FGF4-FOSL1, CSNK1A1-FGF4-FOSL1, DVL1-FGF4-FOSL1, FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4 and FGF4-FOSL1-PPP2CA. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of EP300-FOSL1-X combinations

Williams et al. [23] utilized Dupuytren's disease (DD), a common localized fibrotic disorder, to evaluate the impact of epigenetic regulation of myfibroblasts and identify potential tractable targets in human fibrosis and demonstrate that the epigenetic regulator CREBBP/EP300 is a critical determinant of the profibrotic phenotype. To investigate the role of EP300-regulated transcription factors in profibrotic gene expression, they performed siRNA-mediated gene knockdown of FRA1/FOSL1, RUNX1, and TEAD4 in DD myfibroblasts and demonstrated that knockdown of FOSL1 significantly increased expression of genes like CXCL8, IL6, and CTGF, and inhibited CCL26, SFRP4, and COL6A3 expression. Together, their data supported the role of EP300 in modulating diverse profibrotic pathways and identified RUNX1, TEAD4, and FRA1/FOSL1 as EP300-associated transcription factors that regulated discrete gene

modules in myofibroblasts.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for EP300 along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-EP300-FOSL1 and EP300-FGF4-FOSL1. Also, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for SFRP4 along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-FOXN1-SFRP4, FOSL1-SFRP1-WNT2B, FOSL1-NKD1-SFRP4, FOSL1-GSK3A-SFRP4, FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1, FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SFRP4, FOSL1-FZD2-SFRP4, FOSL1-PORCN-SFRP1, FOSL1-MYC-SFRP4, FOSL1-SFRP1-TCF7 and FGF4-FOSL1-SFRP4. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.7. Examining the behaviour of DKK1-FOSL1-X combinations

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) infection is a significant and independent risk factor for gastric cancer (GC). Dickkopf-related protein 1 (DKK1) is a WNT signaling antagonist, and cytoskeleton-associated protein 4 (CKAP4) is a newly identified DKK1 receptor. Luo et al. [24] hypothesize that *H. pylori* induced activation of DKK1/CKAP4 signaling contributes to the initiation and progression of GC. They identified JUN, FOSL1, and DKK1, and confirmed that the three proteins and CKAP4 were highly expressed in *H. pylori* infected GC cells and gerbil gastric tissues, and human GC tissues. They show that JUN and FOSL1 form AP-1 to transcriptionally activate DKK1 expression by binding to the DKK1 promoter and activated DKK1 bound to CKAP4 to promote GC cell growth, colony formation, migration, invasion, and xenograft tumor growth in nude mice. All these effects were driven by activation of the PI3K/AKT/mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for DKK1 along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DKK1-FOSL1-FRAT1, DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB, DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2, DKK1-FGF4-FOSL1 and DKK1-DVL2-FOSL1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.8. Examining the behaviour of FRZB-FOSL1-X combinations

Nonsynonymous polymorphisms in the human FRZB gene have been associated with osteoarthritis (OA). Lories et al. [25] demonstrated that deletion of the FRZB gene in mice increased cartilage damage in different models of OA and FRZB^{-/-} mice show increased cortical bone density. In healthy cartilage of FRZB^{-/-} mice, four genes were consistently expressed at lower levels than in the wild-type mice: CTNNA1, CTBP1, FOSL1 and MYC. In contrast, WNT8B expression was upregulated in healthy cartilage in 2/3 samples from FRZB^{-/-} versus wild-type mice and in all samples in affected versus healthy wild-type cartilage. Further, CTBP1 and FOSL1 were also downregulated in all samples from arthritic wild-type mice versus healthy ones. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for FRZB along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-FRAT1-FRZB, FOSL1-FOXN1-FRZB, and DKK1-FOSL1-FRZB. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.9. Examining the behaviour of CCND-FOSL1-X combinations

In colorectal carcinoma (CC) tissues, Liu et al. [19] show that the transcription factor FOSL1 activates the expression of SMURF, which can bind to the tumor suppressor FBXL2 and promote the ubiquitination and degradation of FBXL2, thereby activating the β -catenin nuclear translocation and elevating the expression of downstream genes such as c-MYC and CCND1 to promote the growth and metastasis of CC cells. In their review Sobolev et al. [26] state that FOSL1-dependent induction of CCND1 occurs due to the induction of the transcription factor DMP1 that FOSL1 controls. Further, they point that FOSL1 mRNA carries the binding sites of the following miRNAs miR-34A-C/221/222/149/138. Respectively, in the cells that overexpress the mentioned mi-RNA, FOSL1 mRNA will likely be degraded and on the other hand, each mi-RNA has multiple target genes, i.e., FOSL1 is not going to be the only gene that mi-RNA destroys. For example, miR34a and miR34b/c target CCNE2, AXL, LMNB2, CDK4/6, NOTCH1, E2F3, MYCN, SIRT1, MET, CCND1, BCL2, ZEB1, etc., thus interfering with the normal flow of cell proliferation and causing cell cycle arrest in the G1 phase and promoting cell apoptosis and senescence. Thus, overexpression of these mi-RNAs might promote the development of adverse effects. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CCND family along with FOSL1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-FGF4-FOSL1, FZD5-CCND3-FOSL1, APC-CCND3-FOSL1 and FZD5-CCND2-FOSL1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of FOSL1 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the FOSL1, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For FOSL1, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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